

OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES COORDINATION REPORT

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D2.1 – Observational studies coordination report

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.1 of the TAICo (Teacher-AI Complementarity project) focuses on the coordination of observational studies across TAICo academic partners. Its purpose is to provide a project-wide overview of how teacher-AI complementarity is being investigated around the TAICo Framework.

The TAICo Framework structures the analysis of complementarity at three levels: task, skill, and job, while situating these within specific teaching contexts, teacher knowledge, AI-Ed system properties, and deployment conditions.

Deliverable 2.1 outlines how TAICo cases are described and coordinated across partners to address the project's aim: understanding how teachers and AI systems complement each other. The cases are described in terms of their methodological approaches, contexts, and expected outcomes, covering variations in teaching contexts, learner ages, teacher characteristics, AI-Ed systems, research methods and modes of execution.

Coordination within the project ensures alignment with key project results: the development of Complementarity Model (R1), the Knowledge Base (R2), Development and Deployment Guidelines (R3), Teacher Training Guidelines (R4) and Roadmap and Policy Recommendations (R5). The process of coordination is iterative, involving dialogue among partners and regular consortium meetings. This approach ensures that cases remain complementary to each other and contribute to the overall project goals.

Section 2 of the Deliverable 2.1 “The TAICo Framework” presents the TAICo framework and explains the three levels of complementarity (tasks, skills, and jobs) and the contextual factors that shape teacher-AI interaction. It further describes the teacher characteristics, the features of AI-education systems, and the conditions of AI deployment. These dimensions provide a shared language and structure for TAICo cases and for exploring how teacher-AI complementarity unfolds across different contexts.

Section 3 “Coordination of TAICo Cases” outlines how observational studies are organised and aligned across each project partner. Each of the coordinated cases represents unique contributions to understanding teacher-AI complementarity. Together the cases provide diverse perspectives on how AI can complement teachers' professional practices, enhance student outcomes and inform the development of theory, AI-Ed design principles, and teacher professional development. The section also provides detailed case descriptions, highlighting cases' aims, contexts, teacher and AI roles, and expected contributions.

Section 4 “Observational Study Methods” outlines the role and purpose of the observational studies conducted within TAICo project. The studies, carried out by the six academic partners, form a core component of Tasks 1.3 and 2.2. Observational cases' main goal is to examine how teachers and learners interact with AI in real educational settings, aiming to reveal how AI reshapes teacher tasks, skills, and roles. By covering diverse educational levels, subjects, and AI tools, the studies collectively provide an evidence base for understanding teacher-AI complementarity. The findings of the observational studies contribute both to the development of TAICo Knowledge Base and to the implementation of the later project phases.

Section 5 “Observational study contributions to TAICo model development” further explains how the observational studies contribute to the development of the TAICo model by generating empirical evidence on teacher-AI interaction across different levels: task, skill and job.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the coordination of the TAICo cases in terms of research design and overall expected contribution to the project. This document provides an overview of the project-level methodological approach of TAICo and explains the key categories of concepts, the concepts, and examples of those concepts around which TAICo research is oriented. It then provides detailed descriptions of the TAICo cases in terms of these key concepts, giving a project-wide overview of the diverse research designs and aims that constitute TAICo.

By mapping the cases in terms of the teachers, AI-Ed systems, and contexts that they focus on, this deliverable provides stakeholders with a detailed view of the multifaceted and diverse views of teacher-AI complementarity across the project. It highlights the extent to which characteristics of the teacher, AI-Ed systems, and their contexts are seen as impacting changes to the tasks teachers carry out, the skills that teachers possess and require, and the profession to which teachers belong. The coordination of TAICo cases is carried out in consideration of T1.3: Theoretical model development, T3.3 Prototyping interfaces for teacher-AI interaction, and T4.3 Professional learning initiatives. Each of these three tasks along with this deliverable's constituent task T2.1 Preparation of Cases and Coordination of the observational and design studies together represent the first propositions of TAICo Results 1-4, thus setting the direction for the majority of the scientific output of the project.

2. TAICo Framework

To understand the interaction between human and AI skills that TAICo investigates, the project initially developed the TAICo framework, referred to in the proposal as the *Model on Teacher-AI Complementarity*. To avoid confusion between this broader, socio-technical framework and the more specific model on task- and skill-level changes in teaching (which will be produced as Result 1 of the TAICo project), the original model is now referred to as the *TAICo Framework*. Throughout this document, the term *TAICo Framework* is therefore used to describe the overall socio-technical system that guides the project's research.

The TAICo framework (Figure 1) is a project-level tool for orienting each of the TAICo cases to the central concepts and phenomena that the project studies. In essence, the TAICo framework considers changes to the task-, skill-, and job-level characteristics of teaching that AI complementarity may bring by relating these changes to characteristics of the teacher, characteristics of the AI-Ed system, and characteristics of the deployment of the AI-Ed system. The framework also orients each case to consider the context of the teaching job and task that each of its constituent studies situates itself within.

Figure 1. The TAIcO Framework (number refer to the subsequent sections of this document)

Each TAIcO Framework section is described here, with descriptions of each subsection also provided. While cases are coordinated so that they are described across the sections and subsections, the sections and sub-sections of the TAIcO framework are neither prescriptive in the sense that each case must explicitly consider every section nor are examples in each subsection meant to be an exhaustive list of the potential ways that cases may touch upon these subsections. Instead, in terms of coordinating the cases, the TAIcO framework is an orienting and descriptive tool meant to guide systematic description of rich research output from cases, including the possible future development in the cases through participatory design in WP3 and WP4. The framework orients the project towards a shared language of relation and interrelation of research foci in order to inform all TAIcO project-level results, especially focusing on R2, the TAIcO Knowledge Base, and is iteratively developed further throughout the project lifetime.

2.1 Complementarity in the Hybrid Intelligent System

In TAIcO, the assemblage by which a teacher dynamically shares tasks and decisions with an AI-based system is referred to as a Hybrid Intelligent System (Cukurova et al., 2019, Holstein et al., 2020). Consistent with this framing is a notion of change, complementarity, or co-evolution between the constituent members of the system (Järvelä et al., 2025), in this case, the teacher and the AI. TAIcO considers this complementarity comprehensively across multiple levels of granularity for understanding teaching, including task-, skill-, and job-level perspectives on education and how it will evolve with Artificial Intelligence. This part of the TAIcO framework will be developed as the *Model of Complementarity* in WP1 (Result 1 of the project).

2.1.1 Task-level

The task-level perspective on teaching is the first perspective at which TAICo considers complementarity. Building on prior work in this area (Molenaar, 2022), TAICo cases consider the extent to which particular tasks within a teacher's work are replaced, complemented, or augmented by AI. In this view, replacement entails an AI system completely taking over the task for a teacher. Complementing involves a teacher and an AI system performing a task through a reciprocal interaction by which both parties execute specific subtasks or take specific roles. Augmentation occurs when teachers' skills are enriched by AI to enact new tasks that enrich their teaching by going beyond the tasks accomplished by a teacher alone.

2.1.2 Skill-level

Teachers' tasks and the complementarity between teacher and AI directly affect the skill-level changes introduced through teacher-AI complementarity. This perspective includes focus on changes to demands on teachers' knowledge, viewed through models like the Intelligent-TPACK framework (Celik, 2023) which considers how ethical applications of AI in teaching intersect with content, pedagogical, and technological knowledge. It likewise considers teachers' situation-specific skills like professional noticing (Van Es & Sherin, 2021) and decision-making which guide teachers' navigation of classroom situations (König et al., 2022) and which may be supported by AI systems as prior research has proposed (Tammets & Ley, 2023; Karumbaiah et al., 2023).

2.1.3 Job-level

At a broader level, TAICo considers teaching on the job-level and considers the effect of teacher-AI complementarity on the risk of automation and the opportunities for transformational change that the teaching profession may face. Existing work is looking at AI effects on job-level changes classified the teaching profession as a low-to-intermediate level risk of automation (Lassébie & Quintini, 2022). Emerging research like that of the TAICo cases must continue to consider how in a hybrid intelligent system, interaction between teacher and AI change the constituent tasks and skills of teaching. These emerging changes may in turn impact both the set of tasks and skills which are considered fundamental to the profession and how teacher-AI interaction and complementarity add new potential to the demands and value of the profession.

2.2 Context

In order to make specific and contextualized claims about the complementarity between teachers and AI, each TAICo case situates its research in a particular teaching context described across a variety of dimensions. While the subcomponents of this section broadly may help define many cases, other contextual elements such as pedagogical-didactical models used in teaching or stages in these models that come into focus should also be used to contextualize TAICo cases when relevant.

2.2.1 Teaching Job

TAICo cases consider the teaching profession broadly, including teaching across various professional settings. The teaching job subcategory considers settings such as schools, higher education institutions, professional training organisations, and settings which support instruction such as learning design.

2.2.2 Career Stage

TAICo considers the teachers within its cases in terms of their own career stage, including pre-service teachers in teaching-training educational programs as well as in-service teachers at varying levels of teaching experience and AI experience.

2.2.3 Teaching Task

Cases are not confined only to research on implementation of teaching, but may consider any combination of designing, planning, implementation, evaluation and reflection among the tasks that constitute the teaching job.

2.2.4 Student Outcomes

TAICo cases likewise take a broad view on how and whether its cases define the outcomes for students who experience teaching which is complemented by AI. While traditional learning outcomes such as content mastery may be considered by some cases, others may focus on learning process-level outcomes such as traces of self-regulatory, problem-solving, and collaborative processes in learning, reflecting transversal skills required of learners as highlighted in the European Skills Agenda (European Commission, 2023).

2.3 Teacher Characteristics

Just as the complementarity model focuses on various perspectives on teachers and teaching with a focus on how they will change or be complemented by AI, the TAICo framework uses similar lenses to consider the characteristics of the teacher as their own part of the broader dynamic system. It may be important for cases to consider even the characteristics of the teacher which are not a particular focus of complementarity in a given study insofar as these characteristics may influence or moderate the effect of complementarity.

2.3.1 Knowledge

Teacher knowledge is understood in TAICo through the TPACK framework (Archambault & Barnett, 2010), framework from research on technology-enhanced learning which describes different types of knowledge needed by teachers: Technical Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), Content Knowledge (CK), and the overlaps between these types of knowledge. More recent work has added ethical application of AI to this framework (Celik, 2023), considering also the overlap between those knowledge types and AI knowledge.

2.3.2 Situation-specific Skills

Whereas the TPACK model broadly defines categories of skills including skills which require pedagogical knowledge, TAICo cases may also focus more specifically on the constituent situation-specific skills that teachers use to guide their behaviour in the classroom. For these situation-specific skills, TAICo considers models mainly known as noticing, which identify perception, interpretation, and decision making as three core situation specific skills which define their teaching performance (Van Es & Sherin, 2021).

2.3.3 Metacognitive Skills

In addition to pedagogical skills and content-area expertise, TAICo cases may also consider teachers' metacognitive skills. Teachers' metacognitive awareness moderates their abilities to carry out metacognitive processes such as planning, goal setting, monitoring of their own and their students' cognitive processes, and regulation of their own and their students' learning. Drawing on prior study of teachers' metacognitive processes (Duffy et al., 2009) TAICo cases may be sensitive to how planning and reflection upon teaching impact teachers' effectiveness in carrying out their other tasks.

2.3.4 Beliefs and Attitudes

In addition to skills and knowledge, teachers also bring beliefs and attitudes to their teaching which may both influence AI complementarity and which may be subject to change over time in cases of complementarity. TAICo cases may therefore consider the beliefs teachers have about pedagogy (Leder et al., 2002), about their own self-efficacy as teachers (Capara et al., 2006), and the beliefs they have about educational technology (Kim et al., 2013) as interacting with the skills and knowledge they have in these areas.

2.4 AI-Ed System

Just as teachers must be considered as an individual component of a Hybrid Intelligent system, so to must the AI-Ed systems which are implemented in the TAICo cases. TAICo cases therefore consider various aspects of the AI-Ed system as potentially relevant variables to complementarity.

2.4.1 Specific purpose

AI-Ed systems in the TAICo project are considered broadly with various and sometimes multiple AI abilities or tasks making up a given implementation. TAICo cases should be thorough in describing these purposes, including examples like text and image generation, intelligent tutoring systems, natural language processing, computer vision, and data mining to name only some. In this way, just as the abilities and tasks performed by teachers are considered for each case, so too are the tasks and abilities of the AI-Ed system.

2.4.2 Usability

TAICo cases may also consider the interactional usability of the AI-Ed systems they feature. This may be through describing design processes, usability evaluation results, or other descriptions of the interaction such as the reliability or accuracy of the system.

2.4.3 Interface

The AI-Ed systems in TAICo should likewise be clear in the extent to which human control is present in the system. Terming AI-Ed systems as human-in-the-loop (decisions have human input), human-on-the-loop (decision may be overridden by humans), or human-out-of-the-loop (decisions are made without human control) may be fruitful and can be done at the overall system level as well as at the level of component system models.

2.4.4 Algorithms

Describing the architecture of the algorithms underlying the AI-Ed systems in TAICo cases is also important, differentiating rule-based, symbolic AI systems from simple machine learning architectures and multilayered deep learning architectures. Insofar as different algorithms may be more theory-guided or more data-driven and different algorithms may themselves change more or less over a given study, this consideration impacts both the complementarity within a case and the interpretation of the case results.

2.4.5 Models

TAICo cases may likewise have different types of model output processes, ranging from highly probabilistic stochastic models that may be used for example by generative systems to more rigidly deterministic models with predictable outputs for a given input. These differences likewise may impact both the complementarity and interpretation of results within cases, so careful attention must be paid to these differences across TAICo cases.

2.5 Deployment of AI-Ed

Finally, just as the teacher and the AI-Ed system must individually be considered in their interplay with complementarity, so too must the deployment or implementation of AI. Similar to the context factors which specify the conditions of the teacher and the teaching, the deployment of AI-Ed factors put into context the overall Teacher-AI interaction.

2.5.1 AI-Ed Adoption Factors

Adoption of AI by a given teacher or institution depend not only on the individual teacher and AI-Ed system but also on a variety of community, attitudinal, and workplace systemic factors (Cukurova et al., 2023). For that reason, understanding the broader AI-Ed adoption contexts for cases, both in the experimental strand of TAICo cases and in the design-based research strand, should be considered carefully.

2.5.2 Ethical and Social Considerations

The social and ethical backdrop in which teacher-AI interactions occur will also be an important contextual factor in TAICo cases. This backdrop includes a wide range of considerations, including AI trust and trustworthiness which has been shown to interact with AI adoption (Nazaretsky et al., 2023), as well as ethical considerations like fairness, bias, and transparency which are part of teachers' AI knowledge in the Intelligent-TPACK framework (Celik, 2023).

3. Coordination of TAICo Cases

TAICo outcomes are powered centrally by the TAICo Cases. TAICo cases are carried out by the six TAICo academic beneficiaries, with each beneficiary carrying out one study in each of the two phases of the project for each of the two research strands of the project. As such, each beneficiary carries out four total studies, distributed across one or more cases of teacher-AI complementarity.

TAICo includes both an experimental research strand and a design-based research strand for its studies. In Phase 1 (M1-M12) of the project, TAICo takes an exploratory approach, with studies in the experimental strand taking the form of observational studies and those in the design-based research strand taking the form of participatory design studies. In Phase 2 (M13-M36) of TAICo, the project takes a confirmatory approach, with experimental field studies and design-based implementation and evaluation studies. The TAICo Methodology is visualized in Figure 2, describing the interrelation of studies within a phase and the direct transference of results from studies in Phase 1 to designs of corresponding studies in Phase 2.

Figure 2. The TAICo Methodology

Insofar as the TAICo cases should cover a wide range of the different contexts, characteristics, and situations which can be described in the TAICo framework, TAICo case coordination involved active dialogue and negotiation between partners between the start of the project through the first consortium meeting in March 2025 and through to the production of this deliverable. Concurrently, weekly task-force meetings were convened by WP2 from the start of the project and are ongoing. These meetings focus on specific issues across the cases such as observational study methods or transfer of observational study findings into participatory study designs. In these studies, representatives from each case update the consortium and jointly re-align case-level and project-level aims.

As the coordination report describes both ongoing and completed research by partners as well as intended research which will begin in the second phase of the project, the coordination of TAICo cases is a live and ongoing process, with coordination tasks and reporting thereof existing as a shared responsibility between academic partners as part of Work Package 2, led by UOULU. As such, the coordination table reports case information as reported by partners following the first consortium meeting and updated in preparation of the second consortium meeting in October 2025.

Case coordination tables are oriented around reporting the relevant factors of the TAICo Framework. Insofar as each case differs in its specific contextual and methodological details, case coordination tables do not strictly list TAICo framework categories and subcategories as table columns. Instead, these categories are openly presented in descriptions of the cases, their methodologies, and their aims.

3.1 UOULU: MAI – A Metacognitive AI Agent for Supporting Teachers in Collaborative Learning Contexts

Section	Field	Description
Case Overview	Summary	<p>MAI is a Metacognitive AI agent aimed at recognizing challenges to collaborative learning and supporting regulation of learning by inviting students to raise their metacognitive awareness through spoken prompts. MAI understands students' speech via off-the-shelf deep-learning speech recognition models and uses a rules-based approach to recognize collaborative learning challenges based on the triggers for self-regulated learning framework (Järvelä & Hadwin, 2024).</p> <p>We will co-jointly empirically investigate the trigger regulation framework and the design of MAI by implementing MAI in secondary</p>

		<p>school science classrooms over several weekly class sessions. By supporting challenges to collaborative learning, MAI aims to build students metacognitive skills and reduce the burden on teachers in monitoring several small groups simultaneously during collaborative learning tasks.</p>
	Expected contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main contributions: Evidence and support learners’ metacognitive monitoring and SSRL skills • Minor contributions: Evidence and support teachers’ use of AI for recognition and facilitation of metacognitive monitoring and SSRL skills. <p>Design and evaluate an AI speech agent which supports metacognitive processes.</p>
Context	Educational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Secondary education - Collaborative learning - Stakeholders involved: students, teachers, school administrators
	Challenges Addressed	Supporting students’ metacognitive skills in collaborative learning contexts by recognizing when challenges to collaboration are inhibiting learning and inviting regulation of learning.
	The role of teachers	Noticing moments in which collaborative learning is inhibited. Prompting students to engage in regulatory processes. Managing classrooms with many small groups of students.
	The role and kind of AI	Transparent rules-based human-on-the-loop system for recognizing triggers for self-regulated learning and delivering pre-recorded, human written prompts to students. Leveraging a stochastic, machine-learning speech recognition model.
Complementarity	Directionality of change	AI-driven change - The teacher’s tasks change from 1) primarily recognizing triggers for regulation among collaborative groups and

		inviting metacognitive monitoring to 2) understanding students' collaborative learning processes and 3) providing complimentary guidance to groups after AI detects triggers and invites metacognitive monitoring and SSRL.
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3.2 UWK: Teacher-AI Complementarity in the Context of Learning Design

Section	Field	Description
Case Overview	Summary	<p>UWK case will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Phase 1) Explore the current usage and role that AI plays in the Learning Design practices of practitioners like lecturers, trainers and curriculum designers in the context of Continuing Education. • (Phase 2) Conceptualize and develop, together with the relevant practitioners, teacher-AI socio-technical tools and pedagogical approaches that aim to support the identified practices and needs. • (Phase 3) Implement the developed tools/approaches to evaluate/validate their impact through a combination of experimental and longitudinal observational studies.
	Expected contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Phase 1) A map of teacher AI practices and needs for Learning Design • (Phase 2) A co-designed AI-tool for learning design • (Phase 3) Evidence of the impact that the usage of the AI-tool and the related pedagogical approaches have on practitioners' design practices and their professional development
Context	Educational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher Education • Continuing Education (at Danube University Krems) • Stakeholders Involved: Trainers, University Lecturers, Curriculum Designers
	Challenges Addressed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What role can AI play to support the different design tasks that practitioners have to perform? E.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How can AI support practitioners to author and reflect on the impact of their learning activities

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How to enable practitioners to collaborate with AI to design higher-order pedagogically guided learning activities that better support student learning • In which ways the interaction between practitioners and AI can be complementary throughout these different tasks?
	The role of teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Re)conceptualization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Define learning goals ○ Consider the context where the learning activity will happen ○ Explore relevant existing patterns, good practices, or pedagogical theories ○ Consider the different social spaces (i.e., individual, or collaborative) • Authoring <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Formalize the role of the participants in the learning activity ○ Designate the learning resources that will be used in the learning activity ○ Define the learning sequence • Reflection, on the impact that the implemented activity had on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Student learning ○ Teacher practices
	The role and kind of AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generative AI to support a conversational agent that guides teachers to define goals, resources, needs, pedagogical approaches, etc., for the learning activities that they want to design, and that later informs them if the specific activity that they designed matched their goals. If not, the AI will support teachers to better design the learning activities (e.g., lessons) • Supervised Machine Learning (SML) algorithms or Expert Systems that can automatically annotate if specific learning activities meet certain goals or not. Thus, supporting the process of evaluating the learning designs created by teachers. (Note that the implementation of SML or an Expert System might not be necessary, if results show that generative AI could reliably do the same tasks. This will be evaluated in the first year of the project.)
Complementarity	Directionality of change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the short term (observation phase), we will begin by exploring AI-driven change (i.e., how AI influences practitioners)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During the co-design phase, we might explore the mutual influence of practitioners and AI in the context of learning design (e.g., through the implementation of Retrieval-Augmented Generation)
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3.3 TLU: Teacher-AI Complementarity for Facilitating Students’ Collaborative Problem-Solving

Section	Field	Description
Case Overview	Summary	<p>This case investigates how AI-enhanced learning technologies can complement teachers’ abilities to design, orchestrate, and reflect on collaborative problem-solving (CPS) activities in middle school mathematics. Through real-time monitoring, adaptive scaffolding, and reflective feedback, AI augments teachers’ pedagogical decision-making and supports both collaborative and individual learning processes.</p> <p>Use case 1 – Designing CPS activities: AI supports teachers in creating collaborative problem-solving tasks by aligning task structures with pedagogical (CPS) and domain (mathematics) models, ensuring that activities foster both problem-solving strategies and conceptual understanding.</p> <p>Use case 2 – Orchestrating CPS in real time: AI monitors group interactions, such as engagement symmetry and participation balance, to help teachers dynamically adjust instruction through prompts, regrouping, or scaffolding.</p> <p>Use case 3 – Supporting individual learners in groups: AI analyzes students’ problem-solving behaviors within group tasks and provides insights to help teachers address individual learning needs without disrupting collaboration.</p> <p>Use case 4-5 – Assessment and reflection: Teachers use AI dashboards with real-time and aggregated data to assess learning processes and outcomes at individual and group levels. AI-generated summaries and visualizations support teachers’ reflection and refinement of instructional strategies, fostering situation-specific professional skills.</p>

	Expected contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence on teacher–AI complementarity: Empirical insights on how AI-enhanced tools (Co-Track, H5P) complement teachers’ CPS-related tasks, augmenting real-time noticing, interpretation, and decision-making. • Teachers’ situation-specific skills: Understanding how AI support shapes teachers’ ability to perceive, interpret, and act in CPS contexts, linked with CPS process indicators. • Task and skill redistribution: Documentation of how AI augments, complements, or replaces teaching tasks and related skills in CPS design and orchestration. • Design guidelines: Principles for designing AI interfaces (dashboards, prompts) that support teachers without reducing autonomy. • Professional learning insights: Identification of training needs for effective teacher–AI collaboration. • Student-level outcomes: Insights into how CPS competence develops when supported by AI-enhanced environments.
Context	Educational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic school students (in math) • Basic school teachers (in math)
	Challenges Addressed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students often collaborate only at a surface level, focusing on task completion rather than deep, coordinated problem-solving, which makes it difficult to integrate cognitive and social processes effectively. • Teachers, in turn, struggle to translate abstract collaboration indicators into actionable designs and to use real-time interaction data for timely, targeted instructional support.
	The role of teachers	<p>Teachers design, interpret, and act upon AI-supported insights to enhance CPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing tasks: Align CPS activities with pedagogical and domain models • Interpreting AI insights: Use AI-generated indicators to adjust instruction in real time through scaffolding, prompting, or regrouping. • Monitoring individuals: Balance group collaboration with personal learning needs by responding to AI analyses of individual behaviors. • Assessing learning: Evaluate students’ CPS processes and outcomes using AI-supported indicators and guide students’ reflection.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reflecting on practice: Use AI-based feedback for professional reflection, interpreting or overriding AI suggestions to preserve contextual and pedagogical judgment.
	The role and kind of AI	<p>Role of AI: AI supports teachers in designing, monitoring, and guiding CPS by generating data-driven insights and actionable recommendations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design: Suggests CPS task designs aligned with pedagogical and domain models. Group formation: Forms balanced groups based on students' prior knowledge and engagement. Data analysis: Processes multimodal data (logs, speech, writing) to detect participation and engagement patterns. Estimation: Estimates collaboration quality and flags groups needing support. Intervention: Recommends evidence-based instructional actions <p>Kind of AI: LLMs for learning design; rule-based ML for grouping and interventions; VAD and speech-to-text for data analysis; supervised ML (Random Forest) for collaboration quality estimation.</p>
Complementarity	Directionality of change	Overall, the nature of teacher–AI interaction ranges along a continuum from human-driven to AI-driven, with phases of co-evolution in between. In design and reflection, teachers lead and use AI as a supportive tool; in individual problem-solving, AI takes the initiative by identifying patterns and prompting responses; while in orchestration and assessment, teachers and AI influence each other dynamically through continuous feedback and adaptation.

3.4 RU: Teacher-AI Complementarity with the use of GenAI

Section	Field	Description
Case Overview	Summary	<p>In RU case there is the following aim: GenAI during Course design:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secondary school teachers aim to use a GenAI tool to design feedback interventions for project-based assignments. The tool is aimed to be used during the design of the project-based assignment.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool augments the teacher's skills by guiding the assignment outline and the reflection on critical course and learning points. It also enhances the teacher's feedback literacy informing about the different aspects of feedback interventions in terms of A) Timing B) Feedback Focus C) Feedback contingency. Lastly, it complements the feedback interventions that the teacher finally decides based on the tool proposals on different types of feedback. <p>GenAI during course enactment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secondary school teachers are aimed to use a GenAI tool to monitor and control student interactions with GenAI The tool permits the teachers to monitor student interaction with GenAI (e.g., if they copied the AI generated output, how many times they prompted etc) and finetune the prompts (e.g., increase or decrease the prompt number, the length of the AI response etc.)
	Expected contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To support the feedback design on project-based assignments To provide a feedback model based on teacher needs according to their course Learning Design To enhance the feedback literacy of the teachers To provide a tool supporting the course Learning Design
Context	Educational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secondary education Individual learning AI use during the course design Stakeholders involved: students, teachers
	Challenges Addressed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing teachers' feedback literacy Fostering teacher teaching control over the AI generated output Fostering teacher teaching control finetuning the AI output given the course objectives or their particular teaching needs.
	The role of teachers	During course design

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defining the pedagogical goals of the lesson Creates lesson plans, instructional materials, assignments and assessments Describes the different core moments of the assignment where feedback is desired Reflects and potentially adapts the different feedback suggestions provided by the tool Finetunes the different prompting parameters <p>During lesson</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitors students' progress Provides feedback on the fly based on prior suggestion of the tool and the things happening during the course
	The role and kind of AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generative AI to teachers to define feedback interventions for project-based assignments and for monitoring and finetuning student-AI interaction. The AI tool aims to provide teachers with insights on student interactions, provide a shared AI-human control and support teacher feedback literacy. Supervised Machine Learning
Complementarity	Directionality of change	AI influences teacher

3.5 RU: Curriculum Adaptivity

Section	Field	Description
Case Overview	Summary	Snappet is a tool that teachers use for lesson planning. Within Snappet there is an intelligent feature called co-pilot that helps teachers with curriculum adaptivity for math in primary education. That is, teachers get information about individual students and predictive paths those students can take and makes suggestions how to adapt the curriculum to the individual students or to the level of the group as a whole.
	Expected contributions	Since this tool is already widely implemented and used by many teachers, this case will provide insights into how different teacher interact with this tool, and will identify different profiles of teacher-AI complementarity with a tool that

		makes active suggestions to adapt their curriculum.
Context	Educational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary education • Individual learning • AI use during lesson and curriculum planning • Stakeholders involved: students, teachers, business (Snappet), school boards
	Challenges Addressed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be able to present curriculum adaptivity for individual students
	The role of teachers	<p><i>During course planning</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plans core curriculum lessons (essential lessons, repetition lessons, independent practice lessons) for students on their own level <p><i>During lesson</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers check based on suggestions from the tool, adjust their instructions (e.g., they give more attention to some students)
	The role and kind of AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curriculum adaptivity based on analysis of student learning (based on learning goals: and how far the student is within a learning goal) based on how students within the system perform (and then Snappet calculates expected performance based on averages of historic data)
Complementarity	Directionality of change	AI provides information and suggestions for teacher (AI-driven change)

3.6 RUB: Augmenting Teachers Through an Intelligent Tutoring System (Calcularis)

Section	Field	Description
Case Overview	Summary	Calcularis is an adaptive educational software designed to enhance basic mathematical competencies in children. The software facilitates the acquisition of basic numerical skills, including number sense, arithmetic operations, and spatial number representation. Its adaptive algorithm continuously assesses students' progress and adjusts the difficulty of tasks accordingly.

		<p>The software incorporates a coach (dashboard) for teachers that provides detailed student information and enables them to monitor learners' progress comprehensively by providing visual information and progress reports.</p> <p>We will investigate data-based decision-making processes. The observational study will focus on how teachers use learning analyses when students work with an intelligent tutoring system to make data-based decisions about individual support measures. The field study experimentally investigates how variation in the represented learning (progression) data influences teachers' data-based decisions.</p>
	Expected contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main contributions: Supporting teachers in data-based decision-making. • Minor contributions: Evidence of which situation-specific skills can be supported. Promoting metacognitive planning and reflection processes.
Context	Educational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary and Secondary education (first to sixth grade) • “Adaptive” supported math training • Teacher support with a dashboard • Stakeholders involved: students, teachers
	Challenges Addressed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding teachers’ use of AI (rule-based tutoring systems) and exploring how AI supports perception, interpretation, and decision-making • Investigating how dashboard design/represented information affects data-driven decision-making.
	The role of teachers	<p>1) Option to work with or select from predefined material and tasks (guided vs. free training)</p> <p>2) Monitoring and diagnosing students’ progress using information from the classroom and from the dashboard</p> <p>3) Transfer this information into didactic practices and plan further instruction.</p>
	The role and kind of AI	<p>Human-out-of-the-loop, transparent/ accountable, rule-based tutoring systems; stochastic models for task selection, hints, and feedback provision. Automatic analysis of digital trace data from students' input, tracking progress using Bayesian Knowledge Tracing (BKT).</p>
Complementarity	Directionality of change	<p>AI influences teacher (AI-driven change):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The AI tool monitors students' learning progress and interacts with them by providing

		<p>feedback and adaptive task selection based on individual learning progress.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers gain insight into the students' learning behavior via a dashboard. The teacher can adjust specific settings, e.g., the time period represented or the selection of individual students.
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3.7 UCL: Collaboration Analytics for Supporting Students and Teachers in Higher Education

Section	Field	Description
Case Overview	Summary	<p>The Collaboration Analytics Dashboard (CAD) is designed to enhance students' awareness by providing post-hoc insights into their collaborative processes, challenge moments, and regulatory strategies exhibited during group activities. It also aims to support teachers by improving their perceptual awareness, providing help for students in a complex f2f collaborative learning context and enabling informed instructional adaptations in multi-group classrooms.</p> <p>The Multimodal Learning Analytics System collects and analyzes multimodal data—both video and audio—from authentic small-group collaborative learning sessions throughout the semester. It automatically detects challenge moments and regulatory processes from student discourse while inferring group interactions from students' non-verbal communication. The challenge detection models, developed in our prior work (Suraworachet et al, 2024), leverage machine learning and generative AI, whereas the group interaction detection models utilize computer vision techniques, building on our previous research (Zhou et al, 2023).</p> <p>Feedback Generation and Delivery:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For students: Feedback is transparently generated based on expert (teaching team) input and delivered through a group dashboard. For teachers: A teacher-facing dashboard is provided weekly to promote adaptive instruction, foster collaboration, and support students' regulation of learning.

		A prior evaluation with students (Suraworachet et al, 2025) demonstrated the potential of this feedback system in supporting collaboration and regulations. Further studies will be conducted with both students and teachers to refine the analytics feedback design, driving iterative improvements.
	Expected contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main contributions: Evidence and support learners' collaborative learning and SSRL skills • Minor contributions: Evidence and support teachers' use of AI for monitoring and supporting students in collaborative learning contexts in higher education. Design and evaluate human and AI complementarity to support collaborative learning
Context	Educational Contexts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher education • Small-Group Collaborative learning (3-6 students per group) x 6-8 groups per class • Stakeholders involved: students and HE teachers (teaching assistants and a module leader)
	Challenges Addressed	<p>Supporting students' collaborative and regulatory skills in collaborative learning contexts by providing information on their group interactions, along with challenge moments and regulatory processes to enhance post-hoc awareness and promote collaboration and regulation subsequently.</p> <p>Supporting teachers to gain insights into students' collaborative learning process. Addressing the challenges of limited time and attention in the complex teaching context in collaborative learning.</p>
	The role of teachers	Receiving a weekly class report on students' collaboration and regulations, particularly on their challenges, which are further used for providing appropriate support during or after the collaborative learning sessions and adapting instructional design in subsequent sessions, accordingly.
	The role and kind of AI	Stochastic machine-learning and language models are integrated mainly for semi-automatically processing data, translating from video and audio captured to the target constructs

		<p>(group interactions and regulations). To be specific, AI models are leveraged on non-verbal communications to identify speakers and gaze objects and infer the amount of talk, mutuality of discussion, and group interactions. Additionally, language models are used to identify challenge moment dimensions and regulatory processes from students' discourse.</p> <p>The human (teaching team) is involved in data verification, drafting textual feedback and making informed decisions based on the presented information.</p> <p>Currently, students only engage with the system as receivers of information with limited interactions with the system.</p>
Complementarity	Directionality of change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-evolution (Mutual influence) • From the teachers' perspective, the proposed AI tools support teachers to monitor the process of collaborative learning and deliver timely support for collaborative learning. Meanwhile, the proposed AI tool may also affect teachers' learning design about CL. • From the AI perspective, the proposed AI can use teachers' feedback as input to improve its model to provide information/feedback/intervention according to teachers' specific/personalized needs.

The tables in this section provide an overview of the six cases, outlining their pedagogical focus, the AI tools they utilize, and the nature of the teacher–AI complementarity they investigate. While these descriptions established the conceptual and contextual foundation of the work, the next step involved concretizing cases into specific observational studies to initiate the first phase of empirical research in the TAICo Project

Chapter 4 therefore focuses on how the cases were operationalised through observational studies - how data were collected, what was observed. This section bridges the general case descriptions with the first empirical work that underpins the initial refinement of the TAICo model, showing how each case generated evidence on teacher–AI interactions in authentic contexts.

4. Observational Study Methods

The TAICo observational studies form a central part of Tasks 1.3 and 2.2 – informing the TAICo model of teacher-AI complementarity as well as contributing to creation of the TAICo knowledge base. Across the six TAICo academic partners, these studies investigate how

teachers and learners interact with AI in authentic educational contexts, aiming to reveal how AI transforms teacher tasks and skills. While each case focuses on a specific learning or teaching context, together they make it possible to represent a wide range of educational levels, subjects, and AI tools.

Partner & Case name	Observational case focus	Methods
UOULU - MAI: A Metacognitive AI Agent	The case explores how a metacognitive AI agent MAI supports socially shared regulation of learning (SSRL) during a collaborative physics task. The AI agent detects moments when groups face challenges: cognitive, socioemotional, behavioral, or metacognitive difficulties, or a lack of shared perspective, and provides adaptive prompts to help learners socially regulate. The aim is to increase the groups' metacognitive awareness and support SSRL. The case examines how students respond to the AI's interventions and how teachers participate in or guide AI-supported interactions.	Analysis is based on transcribed video recordings of classroom interactions collected during collaborative physics tasks supported by a metacognitive AI agent. The goal is to understand how groups of students interact with the AI agent for socially shared regulation of learning (SSRL) present and what role the teacher plays in these interactions. The analysis focuses on how teachers, students, and the AI communicate during the task, how learners respond to the AI's prompts, and how moments of shared understanding are established or break down. Using discourse analysis, the study identifies patterns of interaction and examines how the teacher and AI jointly support students' socially shared regulation of learning.
UWK: Supporting Practitioners to Design Learning Activities with AI	The case focuses on how teachers and learning designers use an AI chatbot iChat in designing learning activities. The case involves 15 participants who took part in a workshop aimed at improving the quality of learning designs, enhancing students' critical thinking, and creating AI-proof tasks. The focus is on understanding how educators interact with AI during the design process,	The study was conducted through an observational workshop followed by interviews. During the workshop, teachers designed learning activities with support from the AI chatbot, while researchers observed their interactions and design decisions. Seven follow-up interviews provided deeper insights into teachers' reasoning and experiences. The data comprising observation notes, design artifacts, and interview transcripts were analyzed qualitatively to identify patterns of teacher-AI collaboration and good practices in using AI for pedagogically grounded learning design.

how they evaluate and adapt AI-generated ideas, and what constitutes effective teacher-AI collaboration.

TLU: Design of lesson plans with GenAI

Focus: How teachers integrate **GenAI** tools into authentic lesson design and how TPACK, SRL and PID skills shape productive collaboration with AI.

Who: 8 secondary and vocational school teachers from different subjects

Think-aloud observation design in which teachers planned a one-hour lesson using AI tools while screen sharing and verbalizing their thoughts. Each session was followed by a short reflection interview. The data included screen recordings, transcribed think-aloud protocols, and reflective comments.

The data were coded on three levels: (1) situation-specific skills using the perception–interpretation–decision model, self-regulated learning processes and TPACK knowledge domains

RU: Curriculum adaptivity

The case uses the Snippet Co-pilot tool to adapt the curriculum with support from AI. The case examines the different forms of teacher-AI collaboration that emerge as teachers interact with the tool and how these collaborations evolve over time. The focus is on how teacher characteristics, beliefs, and attitudes influence their collaboration with the AI system and how these interactions shape curriculum adaptivity. The case also looks at how changes in the tool affect collaboration patterns and how these patterns relate to students' learning experiences and outcomes.

The case used several instruments to collect both qualitative and quantitative data. The research cycle began with a baseline questionnaire, followed by mini-questionnaires administered biweekly to track ongoing changes. In each cycle, interviews, think-aloud sessions, and log data were collected to gain deeper insights into participants' experiences and actions. Classroom observations were also conducted to capture authentic teaching and learning practices.

The analysis focused on interviews, think-alouds, and classroom observations. Qualitative analyses were carried out using Atlas.ti on interview and think-aloud data. The findings were further examined using Hierarchical Task Analysis, combining observation and think-aloud data.

The study explored teacher–AI collaborations by identifying pedagogical practices before and with AI, analyzing attitudes, and detecting patterns in how teachers worked with AI. Teachers were clustered based on collaboration types, categorized as replace, complement, or augment.

<p>RUB Promoting teachers' ability to provide adaptive support for students' basic skill development in math with an ITS</p>	<p>The case focuses on how teachers use learning analytics to identify students who need additional support and make data-based decisions for individualized interventions. It explores how teachers interpret AI-generated insights, verify the information, and decide when and how to act on the system's suggestions.</p>	<p>The study involves primary and secondary teachers. Data were collected from three pilot participants, with plans to expand to 10–15 teachers. The methods included screen recordings of teachers' behavior combined with think-aloud protocols to capture insights into their cognitive processes while using AI tools. In addition, semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore teachers' experiences and reflections. A questionnaire was used to gather background information on teachers' diagnostic competence, AI-TPACK, teaching experience, and use of AI in their practice.</p>
<p>UCL: Collaboration analytics for supporting students and teachers in higher education</p>	<p>The case focuses on how an AI tool is used to help teachers monitor and support students' collaborative learning, revealing group dynamics, participation patterns, and cognitive challenges. The study examines how teachers integrate AI insights into their reflection and planning, and what role they play in interpreting and acting on AI feedback.</p>	<p>The study was conducted in authentic classroom settings with around 40 students. Data were collected through teacher reflections, classroom observations, and AI-generated reports on group collaboration. teachers' practices were compared before and after introducing the AI tool, analyzing how it influenced their monitoring, interpretation, and intervention strategies.</p>

Across the consortium, the observational studies in Phase I provide an evidence base for understanding teacher -AI complementarity in authentic educational contexts. Each case examines how AI supports different aspects of teaching and learning, from lesson design and orchestration to feedback, adaptivity and collaborative learning. Together, these studies inform the development of the TAICo Knowledge Base (Result 2) and contribute to the design and deployment work in WP3 and WP4. The table summarizes the focus and methodological approach, highlighting their contribution to specific levels of teacher-AI complementarity (task, skill, knowledge/attitudes, job).

5. Observational study contributions to TAICo results

Each of the TAICo cases focuses not only on broadly carrying out the work of the project but specifically focusing on contributions to each of the major work packages for which research results are produced by the project, namely WP1, WP3, and WP4.

In the observational phase, cases directly inform WP1 and contribute toward the initial model of Teacher-AI complementarity by making empirical observations at the task-, skill-, and job-

level in various teaching contexts. This contributes to the development of the model of teacher-AI complementarity (see Sec. 5.1). Observational studies also motivate the participatory design work in the project that is conducted in WP3 and WP4. While this work is still ongoing, we briefly describe the foreseen contributions in Section 5.2.

5.1 The role of observational studies for the development of the model of complementarity (WP1)

Work package 1 is responsible for producing TAICo Result 1: the model of teacher-AI complementarity (D1.1). In considering how cases aim to contribute to this work package and result, the perspectives of skill-, task-, and job-level changes are considered from the TAICo Framework. The following table summarizes each case’s contribution to understanding these perspectives.

Case	Expected Contribution
UOULU	<p>The observation phase focuses on evidencing of trigger regulation conceptual framework by deploying the Metacognitive AI Agent MAI in upper secondary classrooms.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task level: By analysing teacher AI interactions in collaborative lessons before and after introduction of the tool, we will locate what the AI agent can reliably detect and prompt, what still requires teacher interpretation and action, and how the orchestration plan shifts. This may pinpoint to complementation at monitoring and prompting, partial replacement in trigger detection, and augmentation through wider coverage. • Skill level: By observing how teachers support students’ regulatory responses AI prompts, we will see which coaching moves intensify, which new skills emerge such as judging AI prompt quality, and managing attention across groups, and how cognitive load moves from class monitoring to data interpretation. • Job level: By comparing time use and responsibility before and after, we will check whether capacity is freed for high value interactions, identify any new routine work and whether teachers would feel comfortable with using this in their work.
UWK	<p>The observation phase includes observations and interviews that provide evidence on how teachers use AI for designing a learning activity and reflecting not its outcome. These activities provide a mapping one existing teacher practices and needs, as well as limitations of AI systems.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task level: Insights on how teachers use AI to define goals, choose pedagogical approaches, and generate materials. Evidence on the reliability of existing AI systems for this purpose. • Skill level: How AI impacts teachers’ planning skills, how teachers interact with AI, and how they evaluate and integrate AI output in the materials they create. • Job level: How AI integration impacts teachers’ cognitive load, reflective skills, decision making. Moreover, how teachers' perception

of AI, in terms of trust, transparency, control, impacts its adoption as part of teachers' practices.

TLU

In the observation phase, the case provided insights into Use Case 1, the design of lesson plans:

- **Task level:** how GenAI can support teachers in lesson design by complementing design activities, generating ideas and structuring lesson components. This allows teachers to focus on higher-level instructional decisions, such as aligning learning objectives, choosing pedagogical strategies and considering students' needs.
- **Skill-level:** how the use of GenAI activates teachers' situation-specific skills, regulatory skills, and technical skills. Teachers applied their pedagogical and technological understanding to effectively use GenAI and related learning technologies (e.g., CanvaAI and domain-specific tools), demonstrating the importance of teachers' interpretation skills in evaluating AI-generated suggestions and making informed instructional decisions.
- **Knowledge/attitudes:** how the use of GenAI activates teachers' knowledge dimensions and beliefs related to learning, the domain, technology, and AI. The process highlighted the importance of teachers' Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) in evaluating AI outputs, aligning them with pedagogical goals and maintaining agency in the lesson design process.
- **Job level:** how the use of GenAI influences teachers' roles and professional responsibilities in lesson design. GenAI tools shifted teachers' focus from routine content creation to curating, evaluating, and adapting AI-generated materials

RU –
GenAI

- **Task level:** By analysing teacher and AI interactions across planning feedback moments, drafting comments, aligning with objectives and timing, we will identify how the chatbot helps the teacher learn and design, what and when teachers ask or change about chatbot input, and how designing an assignment shifts and how it affects student outcomes. We may expect complementation in ideation and curation phases, partial replacement of routine drafting, and augmentation through faster iteration and broader coverage of feedback moments and improved teacher knowledge on feedback strategies.
- **Skill level:** By observing how teachers use and edit GenAI outputs, we will see which kind of judgements are newly necessary to learn, which new skills emerge such as prompt specification, quality checks, and how cognitive load shifts from first-draft writing to evaluation and adaptation.
- **Job level:** We will show whether the GenAI tool adds new knowledge requirements that need to be addressed and what it does to their perceived workload and professional role. We will also capture teachers' willingness to adopt and feel comfortable with using such a tool, and the needed conditions for that.

RU –
Curriculum
Adaptivity

Task level: By analysing how teacher and AI work together in the process of designing an adaptive lesson planning and clustering students, we will identify where teachers handoff to AI and want to/needs to perform checks. This includes when the system proposes groups, when the teacher edits, approves, or rejects them. We may expect collaboration patterns such as complementation and/or augmentation in suggesting and checking clusters.

Skill level: By analysing how teachers review and adapt suggested clusters, we will identify which skills and knowledge are needed for that (e.g., combining classroom knowledge with dashboard literacy).

Job level: We will see whether collaboration leads to higher-quality clustering and improved student outcomes. We will also capture teachers willingness to adopt and the needed conditions for it such as trust in the system and on-site support.

RUB

Task level:

- Inform which level of automation enhances or hinders teacher agency by comparing different forms of AI augmentation.
- Exploratory evidence of how teachers use a dashboard for monitoring students' progress and diagnostic judgment processes and what variables may influence them.
- By focusing on how teachers and AI work together during in-class monitoring and planning follow-up instruction, we will explore the handoffs between system alerts and teacher decisions, for example when the system flags individual learning issues.

- Due to partial replacement, we expect differences in in-class student support and distribution of teachers' attention.

Skill level:

- Establish a baseline for how teachers perceive and utilize learning analytics, informing which aspects of decision-making can be augmented by AI.
- Provide insights into how teachers combine their pedagogical knowledge with AI-generated insights to make informed instructional adaptations.

By analysing how teachers perceive and interpret student analytics, we may identify skills and knowledge required, such as disregarding irrelevant information, interpreting mirrored learning data or aligning insights with classroom knowledge.

Job level:

- New practices and routines may appear when learning with an ITS may be implemented in teachers' practices and students' learning.

UCL

- **Task level:** By analysing how the teacher and the Collaboration Analytics Dashboard work together across the cycle of clarifying aims, viewing the dashboard, observing, integrating evidence, considering suggestions, deciding, and delivering feedback, we identify interactions and handoffs between the CAD and teacher. We may expect complementation in monitoring, sense making, and feedback selection, partial replacement of manual scanning/monitoring, and augmentation through faster awareness of collaborative processes.
- **Skill level:** By analysing how teachers review indicators and adapt suggestions, we will see which skills are intensified, for example reading interaction and regulation signals and metacognitive coaching, and which new skills are needed, for example checking model rationales, setting thresholds, and translating analytics into specific feedback moves. Cognitive load may shift from continuous scanning/monitoring to higher level sense making and planning.
- **Job level:** Comparing before and after will show whether collaboration with the dashboard frees time for targeted facilitation and therefore better collaborative processes/perceived satisfaction both at the teacher and student level.

5.2 The role of observational studies for the participatory design phase (WP3 & WP4)

Besides contribution to the development of the model of complementarity, observational studies also contribute more indirectly to participatory design work of the project in WP3 and WP4. Specifically, the observations in the cases have emerged certain problems in the design of complementarity in the use of AI by teachers. For example, it was observed that in particular circumstances teachers were not easily able to interpret AI outputs, visualizations or recommendations (e.g. when AI tools identified student progress or lack thereof), or that

how AI tools were operating remained untransparent to teachers. It was also observed that AI output was uncritically taken up by teachers, or that use of AI (e.g. for lesson planning) did not sufficiently take into account pedagogical knowledge or models.

These emerging problems point to potential difficulties or breakdowns in building effective teacher-AI complementarity and they provide rich input for participatory design in the form of design problems or challenges. These design challenges are currently taken up in TAICo co-design teams focusing either on redesign of AI interfaces and tools (WP3), or the design of pedagogical practices and training for teachers (WP4).

In WP3, these design solutions contribute to TAICo **Result 3: Design Principles and Interaction Prototypes of AI for Complementarity**. The cases focus on how AI technologies can be designed, developed and deployed to complement teachers' professional practices - enhancing, rather than replacing, human expertise. Collectively, the studies provide evidence-based insights and prototype systems that illustrate effective teacher-AI collaboration across design, orchestration, feedback and curriculum processes.

In WP4, the focus shifts from technology design to teacher professional learning and the broader implications of AI integration for the teaching profession. The cases collectively explore how teachers develop the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for effective teacher-AI collaboration, emphasizing the development of situation-specific skills, AI literacy, and ethical awareness. While some cases (e.g., UOULU, TLU) examine how AI-enhanced environments support teachers' real-time decision-making, interpretation, and reflection, others (e.g., UWK, RUB, RU, UCL) focus on professional learning processes and how teachers interpret AI feedback, adapt instructional strategies and sustain agency in AI-supported contexts. Together, the cases collectively explore of how AI-enhanced environments can serve as contexts for professional growth, identifying the skills, attitudes, and training conditions needed for effective teacher-AI collaboration. **These insights feed into Result 4: guidelines and best practices for professional learning.**

Besides contributing to WP1 and WP3 and 4 in Phase I of the project, the Phase II TAICo studies in which confirmatory research tests the designs, guidelines, and principles generated in WP3 and WP4 will also be built on the original insights of the observational studies. An overview of the uptake of results of observational studies is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Role of Observational Studies for subsequent tasks in TAICo

6. Conclusions and future outlook

As TAICo cases now carry out Phase I of the research at the core of the TAICo project, key TAICo tasks including T1.3 (model development), T3.3 (prototyping of AI interfaces) and T4.3 (professional learning initiatives) all are concurrently underway. These tasks are dependent on T2.1 (preparation and coordination of cases), the task for which this coordination report represents an initial deliverable. By orienting case coordination toward the TAICo Framework, these tasks are feasible and in line with the TAICo Methodology, combining experimental and design-based research.

With TAICo cases coordinated and initiated, this deliverable and the work which constitutes it feed into T2.2, the development of an evaluation framework which will further orient TAICo cases, not only in their research design, but also in the analysis and reporting of results so as to inform all TAICo results. This deliverable along with D1.1 (the initial theoretical model of teacher-AI complementarity), D3.1 (the ethical AI taxonomy and initial guidelines for teacher-AI complementarity) and D4.1 (the training framework for AI implementation in professional settings) together serve as the initial propositions for Results 1-4 in the TAICo project. Production of these deliverables, starting with the present deliverable, **signal the transition from the heart of Phase I of TAICo through its end and the beginning of Phase II.**

The present deliverable in particular represents the initial proposition of R2 The TAICo Knowledge Base, the structured collection of all empirical results derived in the studies on effects of AI integration on teachers' profession, job, tasks and skills. The Knowledge Base can only be evidenced by cases which are designed and described systematically, **in order to evidence the relationship between teacher-AI complementarity each of the other components of the TAICo Framework** – teachers, AI-Ed systems, the interactions between

them, and the contexts for these interactions – as well as the interrelations between these components.

With Phase I studies underway across the TAICo project, case coordination focus now shifts toward :

- **Execution** – ensuring that TAICo cases complete their Phase I studies and share results across work packages in time for dependent tasks
- **Evaluation** – agreeing among cases and work packages on the appropriate evaluation methods for designing the Phase II studies to inform all TAICo results
- **Reporting** – sharing scientific and logistical results of Phase I studies internally to prepare for public dissemination and to inform all work packages

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